

EU-HIP

EU INTEROPERABILITY WITH HERA'S IT PLATFORM

Report: Country visit report – Croatia

Date of interviews: 29th-30th November 2023

Work Package: WP4

Lead Beneficiary: Sciensano, Croatian Institute of Public Health (CIPH)

Contributing Beneficiaries: Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), Italian Ministry of Health (MIN-SAL) (development of methodology)

This activity is supported by co-funding from the European Union's EU4Health programme under Grant Agreement Nr 101102774 EU-HIP. Views and opinions expressed do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Abbreviations table

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMR	Antimicrobial resistance
APIs	Application Programming Interfaces
ARDS	Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical
CBRN	Chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear
CEZIH	Central Health Information System of the Republic of Croatia
CIPH / HZJZ	Croatian Institute of Public Health (<i>cro. Hrvatski zavod za javno zdravstvo</i>)
DDD/TID	Defined Daily Doses Per 1000 Inhabitants Per Day
EARS-Net	European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance Network
EC	European Commission
ECDC	European Centre of Disease and Control
ECMO	Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EpiPulse	The European surveillance portal for infectious diseases
EPR system	Emergency Preparedness and Response system
ESAC-Net	European Surveillance of Antimicrobial Consumption Network
EU-HIP	EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform
EWRS	Early Warning and Response System
GLASS	Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System - WHO
HERA	EU Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority
CHIF / HZZO	Croatian Health Insurance Fund (<i>cro. Hrvatski zavod za zdravstveno osiguranje</i>)
IAEA),	the International Atomic Energy Agency
IHR	International Health Regulation
ISKRA	Interdisciplinary Section for the Control of Antibiotic Resistance
ITB tablets	Iodine Thyroid Blocking Tablets
JA	Joint Action
LIS	laboratory information system
MBO	<i>cro. Matični broj osiguranika</i> - registration number of the insured person
MCM(s)	Medical countermeasure(s)
Mol	Ministry of the Interior
NAJS	National Public Health Information System
NFRP	Dutch Fund for Regional Partnerships
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
OIB	Osobni identifikacijski broj - Personal Identification Number
PHPP	Pathogens with high pandemic potential
PoE	Point of entry

PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
SSI	Statens Serum Institute
TESSy	The European Surveillance System - ECDC
UHID	University Hospital for Infectious Diseases (<i>cro. Klinika za infektivne bolesti "Dr. Fran Mihaljević"</i>)
UPIN	Unique personal identifiers numbers
USIE	Exchange in Incidents and Emergencies
WHO	World Health Organisation

INTRODUCTION

This report has been developed within the remit of the project “**EU interoperability with HERA’s IT Platform (EU-HIP)**”. EU-HIP is a consortium of 15 European countries, coordinated by Statens Serum Institute (SSI), Denmark. The scope of the project is to support countries to enhance and improve national IT systems in an efficient and coordinated manner, with the objective of obtaining interoperability with the centralised IT platform of the EU Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA).

HERA's IT platform (ATHINA) is currently under development and seeks to gather intelligence on public health surveillance and medical countermeasures (MCM) to support threat assessment and crisis management across Europe. The priority areas are pathogens with high pandemic potential (PHPP), antimicrobial resistance (AMR), and chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear (CBRN) threats, as well as appropriate medical countermeasures, such as medicinal products, medical devices and personal protective equipment (PPE).

A baseline activity of the EU-HIP project is to perform a landscape assessment of countries' IT systems, in relation to the above-mentioned priorities, across all countries involved in the consortium. In addition, in-depth country visits are being performed in a selected number of countries, to gain detailed insights on the countries' IT systems for health threat detection and assessment.

This report presents the findings from the landscape assessment and in-depth country visit in Croatia.

METHODOLOGY

For the gathering of the information presented in this report, a two-step methodology has been implemented. The overall results, based on the combined methodology, are presented in this report.

a. Landscape analysis

A data-gathering tool was developed by the EU-HIP consortium in close collaboration with HERA, to collect background information on countries' surveillance systems, covering the topics of digital infrastructures and systems, key actors and legislative aspects. By processing the material gathered through this tool, the EU-HIP team has produced an aggregated mapping of the current state of progress in national IT systems supporting collaboration on health threats preparedness and medical countermeasures in Europe (Deliverable 4.1 Landscape Analysis Report).

The tool was shared and supplemented with input from several national experts from different disciplines. This step aimed to gather an initial understanding of the information systems, stakeholders and legislations in place across the different European countries concerning HERA's four priority topics.

b. Country visits

In the second phase, semi-structured interviews are being conducted with experts, delving deeper into each topic. The goal is to gain insights into the functionality of these systems, the roles and interactions of key stakeholders and additional details about pertinent legislations. The interviews build upon the tool's pre-existing questions, encouraging experts to provide additional information beyond what has been already shared during the first main phase. The analysis of the information collected during the country visit is shared with the country of interest for review and after approval, with HERA. The country is also encouraged to publicly share the report to benefit the community. Country-specific materials will also be used to support further work within the EU-HIP project such as the identification of key areas of improvement and the actions needed to achieve interoperability with the upcoming ATHINA platform (Deliverable 5.1 Country Needs Assessment report).

As part of the country visit in Croatia, eight in person and online interviews were performed in November 2023 over two days. An overview of the stakeholders interviewed can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of the stakeholders interviewed as part of the Croatia country visit

Interview date	Stakeholder
Wednesday 29 th November	Croatian Institute of Public Health - Division for Health Informatics and Biostatistics
	Croatian Institute of Public Health - Division for Toxicology
	Croatian Institute of Public Health - Division for Microbiology, Department for Direct Diagnostic Virology
	School of Medicine, University of Zagreb - Department of Environmental and Occupational Health and Sports Medicine
Thursday 30 th November	University Hospital for Infectious Diseases - Department of Clinical Microbiology
	Ministry of the Interior - Civil Protection Directorate, radiological and nuclear, preparedness and response
	Ministry of Health

Within the EU HIP project, the Sciensano team was responsible for conducting the interviews and writing the final report. The country visit was organised with the support of the Croatian National Public Health Institute for the identification of the stakeholders, planning of interviews, provision of additional explanation and revising the report when needed. During the discussions, the interviewers took notes that were summarised afterwards in the form of a report. The interviews were recorded for minutes purposes.

Through the interviews conducted, the different priority areas of interest to HERA were covered as much as possible. The areas covered were AMR, PHPP, CBRN and MCM.

RESULTS

I. Pathogens with high pandemic potential

a. Key actors and stakeholder networks

The **Croatian Institute of Public Health** (Hrvatski zavod za javno zdravstvo – English acronym: CIPH) is the leading public health institution in the Republic of Croatia and counties, founded in 1893. The institute conducts activities in the fields of disease epidemiology, public health promotion, prevention, education and environmental health. CIPH has the central role of coordination of the network of the 21 regional public health institutes (županijski zavodi za javno zdravstvo, one per county and one for the capital city, Zagreb, Nastavni zavod za javno zdravstvo *Dr. Andrija Štampar*). Each regional public health institute is connected to CIPH and is obliged to report health data. Their role is to address public health issues at the local and regional levels, providing services and implementing health programs tailored to the specific needs of their respective areas. They support disease surveillance, health promotion, prevention programs and responding to public health emergencies within their designated regions.

CIPH holds the **Croatian National Reference Laboratory** for the European Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (ECDC), the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the Reference Centre of the Republic of Croatia for the Ministry of Health.

The **Ministry of Health** (Ministarstvo zdravstva) is the primary government body responsible for health policy and regulation and it plays a central role in coordinating efforts related to pathogens with high pandemic potential. It formulates strategies, implements regulations and collaborates with other stakeholders to enhance preparedness.

The **University Hospital for Infectious Diseases** (Klinika za infektivne bolesti **Dr. Fran Mihaljević** – English acronym: UHID) is the leading institution for diagnostics and treatment of infectious disease in Croatia and the surrounding region. As a leading institution for infectious diseases in Croatia, founded in 1893, UHID also serves as the national reference centre for the following areas of expertise: diagnostics and treatment of infectious diseases, viral hepatitis, HIV-infection, urinary tract infections, antibiotic resistance surveillance, tropical and travel medicine and extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) in patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS).

The **Croatian Health Insurance Fund** (Hrvatski zavod za zdravstveno osiguranje – Croatian acronym: HZZO) is the body that administers the universal health care system in Croatia. HZZO is the country's national health insurance fund that assure a universal coverage for all residents of Croatia.

b. Digital infrastructures and systems

i. Data sources

Data collection for infectious diseases can be done following two processes (Figure 1)¹:

- Electronic reporting via the **Central Health Information System of the Republic of Croatia** (Croatian acronym: CEZIH) platform ;
- Paper form reporting, filled by physicians (general practitioners or hospital personnel) and laboratory staff and transfer to one of the 21 regional institutes of public health². Due to the work done to digitalise the procedure since 2023, paper form reporting is only sporadically received.

Figure 1. Notification procedures of a mandatory notification disease

CEZIH³ is the electronic reporting surveillance system at both national and regional level. The system ensures reporting after patient visits, connection with laboratories, submission of laboratory results, pharmaceuticals prescriptions, requests to special health care hospitals, and reporting on infectious disease. Access to CEZIH is granted to authorized users only that is, health care providers contracted by HZZO.

All the information collected, by paper form or electronic reporting, when registering a case of notifiable disease is listed in Appendix 1. Every notification related to mandatory notification diseases is registered and stored in the **Registry of Infectious Diseases**, part of the **National Public Health Information System** (Croatian acronym: NAJS).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, data collection was also performed at designated point of entry (PoE), following the national surveillance protocol. At the end of this period and for the time being, without any recommendation with regard to a specific pathogen, this data collection is no longer in place.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) solutions are not currently used in infectious diseases surveillance in Croatia.

¹ The collection and reporting of laboratory data is not part of the mandatory infectious disease notification process (not mentioned in the mandatory infectious disease legislation: [Protection of the Population from Infectious diseases](#)). For the time being, this data collection is based on voluntary notification and reporting by medical professionals. The only exception is COVID-19, for which every test performed is transmitted to the Infectious diseases register.

² Notification was still a paper-based reporting in March 2023, the electronic application is now in place but health professionals are still able to send a paper-form notification.

³ [Documentation report of CEZIH system - Ministry of Health of Croatia](#)

ii. Data linkage

Croatian health-related information can be recorded through 2 different unique personal identifiers number (UPIN):

- Osobni identifikacijski broj (Personal Identification Number – Croatian acronym: OIB): unique and obligatory number in the whole Croatian public administration system, assigned to Croatian citizens (by birth or citizenship acquisition), or foreign natural persons when there is a basis for their surveillance in the Republic of Croatia (registration in public records and acquisition of the status of the taxpayer). This UPIN is under the responsibility of the Croatian Ministry of Finance – Tax Administration.
- Matični broj osiguranika (Registration Number of the Insured Person – Croatian acronym: MBO): unique number associated with the mandatory social health insurance system for residents of Croatia. This UPIN is under the responsibility of the Insurance infrastructures⁴.

The two UPINs can be linked through Croatia's various IT systems. Inside NAJS, they serve as support of data linkage between 2 or more data sources, the system then generates a personal ID number used for the anonymisation of dataset for use in analysis by scientific and epidemiological teams.

⁴ Croatia applied a universal coverage of health insurance for all residents of Croatia, provided by HZZO. In addition, complementary insurance (for e.g. reimbursement of medications) can be chosen by the individuals either from a public institution (the Croatian Insurance fund) or private (private insurance companies). Most of the Croatian working population has subscribe to a complementary insurance. Additional insurance services can be added to the 2 previous level but only provided by private companies (not common). HZZO is operated by the Ministry of Health.

iii. Data storage

CIPH is the owner of the NAJS system. This system contains several domains associated with different aspects of public health surveillance: health-related services, infectious and non-communicable diseases, causes of death, etc. (Figure 2), divided into specific registries.

NAJS is a storage system of health data and information for their processing and archiving (in health records and registries) to meet and answer national public health needs: control of large processes in health care, assessment of the population's health status, monitoring of chronic diseases, early recognition and response to acute events, support the prevention and strategic planning of actions, etc.

This system integrates information from external institutions to CIPH (e.g. the Health Insurance Fund, the Citizens registry, etc.).

The direct access to data stored in NAJS is restricted by authorities and only registry administrators have access.

Figure 2. Components of the National Public Health Information System of Croatia (NAJS), and interactions.

* domains

CIPH is also the holder of the national public health data warehouse, which supports several health-related systems and platforms, external and internal of CIPH (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Components of the Croatian Public Health Data Warehouse.

**BIS4COVID is an IT system set up during the COVID-19 pandemic to collect all data on hospital journeys (admission to intensive care, respiratory equipment used, length and outcome of stay, etc.) due to a COVID-19 infection, developed under the guidance of the Ministry of Health. Croatian Public Health authorities are now in charge of this system. In a testing phase, and for a broader application to other pathogens/diseases, the BIS4HEALTH system should combine data from Hospitals information systems and Laboratory information systems. Its implementation is still uncertain, other options are also being considered for electronic capture of public health data for public health reports*

A multi-dimensional data model is used to organize data in a database. This organization is based on dimensions (e.g. date, geographical place or code lists) and individual data, coming from different data sources. The patient identification number enables the data integration between the various data sources. This model enables optimised queries, limits data redundancy and speeds the integration processes.

iv. Standards and data quality

Notification of cases of notifiable diseases is not automatically standardised. Practitioners can report cases in the form of free text or by following the national catalogue of standards in health (e.g., common code books used by the Croatian Bureau of Statistics), or international standards for data encoding (e.g., HL7 Clinical Document Architecture, IHE XDS profiles,

ICD- 10 terminology for diagnoses and AR-DRG 5.2 codes for diagnosis related groups). The application of these different standards to the data collection is shown in Appendix 1.

No metadata catalogue is available for infectious diseases data sources. However, work is ongoing to align with the upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS) requirements.

The frequency of laboratory collection depends on the pathogen concerned. For pathogens with rare occurrence, the event is reported when the case is confirmed, whereas for pathogens with common occurrence, such as influenza, a weekly collection is drawn up during a specific period ("*flu season*"). Outside this period, if a detection occurs, the sample is sent to the Influenza Reference Laboratory (CIPH) for further analysis.

Data capture for infectious diseases is not yet digitally automated, manual notification is still used. The only partial exception is for COVID-19, for which automated data collection has been implemented, but manual integration is still performed depending on the laboratories' IT systems for data transfer.

This system allows the export of individual and aggregated data (XML format) for preformatted national reports and international data requests. Business Intelligence systems for reporting are in development by CIPH, a The Centre for shared services (Centar dijeljenih usluga - Croatian acronym: CDU) as a State Cloud and a Data Lake Repository for advanced data analytics are already in preparation.

Reports regarding infectious disease surveillance are regularly produced but only under the request of EpiPulse⁵ (ECDC - European surveillance portal for infectious diseases), with standardised templates (e.g., report on aggregated data for influenza testing, epidemiological report for respiratory virus etc.).

v. Threat indicators

Potential threats are detected by event notification⁶ and indicator surveillance⁷ (individual level notification, number of cases in the population, number of hospital cases, percentage of positive tests in the population etc.) and require the involvement of public health experts. Epidemiologists perform an assessment of the authenticity and accuracy of the threat. If the threat is confirmed, experts are requested to provide suggestions regarding the protection measures and procedures to follow for its management.

⁵ [EpiPulse - the European surveillance portal for infectious diseases - ECDC](#)

⁶ Event-based detection is the organised and rapid capture of information about events that are a potential risk to public health, referring to a method of monitoring and tracking the occurrence of specific health-related events in a population. Health authorities and medical practitioners actively collect and analyse data on specific events, such as cases of illness, hospital admissions or deaths.

Indicator-based is the systematic (regular) collection, monitoring and analysis and interpretation of structured data, to track specific health-related indicators such as incidence or prevalence rates in a population. Health authorities collect and analyse data on specific indicators such as the number of cases of a specific disease, the incidence of hospital admissions or the prevalence of a risk factor.

⁷ Testing strategies are not implemented in a way to allow threshold calculation

In case of the detection of a new threat, regions are ordered to implement the specific testing strategy procedure according to this new threat and report to CIPH. All samples would be sent to CIPH or the University Hospital for Infectious Diseases (Biosafety Level 3 laboratory).

For viruses for which notification is not mandatory but which are still monitored by healthcare professionals and public health institutions, the implementation of prevention measures depends on the willingness of healthcare professionals⁸.

Systematic screening of animals is not in place to detect health threats. However, there is close collaboration between CIPH and the Croatian Veterinary Institute, with information being shared related to testing for pathogens specific to animals (e.g. avian influenza) and for those for which notification is compulsory.

c. Legislation and strategy

Croatia has a specific law regarding the [Protection of the Population from Infectious diseases](#) (Zakon o zaštiti pučanstva od zaraznih bolesti). This law is the basis for legislation on the surveillance and compulsory notification of infectious diseases in Croatia. The list of infectious diseases covered by this legislation is given in Appendix 2. The legislation establishes guidelines outlining how various stakeholders should respond to public health threats associated with communicable diseases. At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, an update was operated to include SARS-CoV-2 in the list. The existing strategy was promptly activated, showcasing the effectiveness of pre-established measures. In addition to addressing known threats, this law provides a mandate to act in the face of unknown threats. Leveraging the country's historical context, researchers possess the knowledge and expertise required to navigate new challenges. These professionals, trained in both medicine and epidemiology, play an essential role in direction of operations in the event of a crisis. Specific protocols guide the response to cases originating abroad. These measures are generally activated in situations such as pandemics, ensuring a targeted response to health threats of an international dimension.

CIPH, and its specific department, is the national contact for international cooperation through the International Health Regulation (IHR), ECDC and the Early Warning and Response System (EWRS).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the Government passed the Disaster Risk Assessment for the Republic of Croatia, based on the [Article 10 – Paragraph 1 of the Civil Protection System Act](#). From this application a long-term strategic planning Act, called [the Disaster Risk Management Strategy \(until 2030\)](#), was created. It fulfils the legal obligation and condition that enables the implementation of EU funds.

NAJS, as part of the state health information structure, is regulated by the [Croatian Act on Data and Information in Health Care System](#) which came into force in 2019. This act regulates rights of processing personal data within the healthcare system, and imposes GDPR-compliant principles, obligations and responsibilities in relation to such processing. It also sets out

⁸ The example of the RSV surveillance: in case of a rising number of positive tests, a circle of communication between laboratories, epidemiologists and paediatricians is put in place for detection, reporting, analysis and prevention communication; a „protocol“ is in place outside the legislation frame.

fundamental principles and standards of their collection, processing and protection. It comes in complement of [the Act on the Implementation of the General Data Protection Regulation](#), enacted in 2018.

The public health national strategy is developed every three to five years, and it involves a collaborative approach wherein experts are invited to contribute with their insights. A particular focus of the strategy is the development of comprehensive protocols to effectively address health challenges such as influenza.

The country has a pre-defined system of headquarters in time of crises, and they are in charge based on their role in the ministry. For a health crisis, the head of the PH institute is a member of the headquarters. Roles are defined in the national strategy and in the standard operating procedures

Evaluation of actions taken during crises is crucial and it should be preferably conducted by external evaluators to ensure impartiality and thorough analysis. In the case of the recent COVID-19 crisis this was not performed until the pandemics ended. This is still an ongoing process in Croatia, but and actions could be taken at the European level for strengthening evaluation procedures.

II. Antimicrobial resistance

a. Key actors and stakeholder networks

The **Croatian Committee for Antibiotic Resistance Surveillance** was established in 1996 at the Croatian Academy of Medical Sciences. It is a network for microbiological laboratories, the catchment of which covers over 90% of the country's population. One of the tasks of the network is to standardise surveillance methodology and laboratory testing methodology. The network meets on a regular basis, although meetings have become less frequent as the work has become more synchronised. The network includes heads of laboratories, infectious disease specialists and clinical pharmacologists.

The **Reference Centre for Monitoring Antibiotic Resistance** of the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare at the UHID *Dr. Fran Mihaljević* was founded in 2003. Its tasks include providing technical support for AMR surveillance and services for the network's activities⁹.

The **Interdisciplinary Section for the Control of Antibiotic Resistance** (Interdisciplinarna Sekcija za Kontrolu Rezistencije na Antibiotike – Croatian acronym: **ISKRA**) was created in 2006. ISKRA coordinates all activities in the area of antibiotic resistance control in human medicine, veterinary medicine, and agriculture, with a One Health approach.

b. Digital infrastructures and systems

i. Data sources

Data on AMR is collected at the national level via the network of microbiological laboratories. The Committee for Monitoring Bacterial Resistance and the Reference Centre for Monitoring Antibiotic Resistance receive all information on antimicrobial resistance from laboratories in Croatia. Each laboratory has a laboratory information system (LIS).

There are several components of the AMR surveillance system:

- *General national antibiotic resistance surveillance*: covers a broad strategy, including all clinical isolates of designated bacterial species. Data for general surveillance is collected on an aggregated basis. Individual level data is only at the level of the local laboratory, to ensure that there are no copy isolates and the isolates are traceable if needed. The reference centre scrutinises the data before analysing them and if anomalies are noted, they report back to the local laboratory.
- *Surveillance of invasive isolates*: part of the European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance Network (EARS-Net) surveillance, covering invasive isolates only (blood and cerebrospinal fluid). For this surveillance, the reference centre receives isolate-based data, including patient demographic information.

Data on isolates are sent and collected electronically at the Reference Centre for Antibiotic Resistance Surveillance located at the UHID *Dr. Fran Mihaljević* and are subjected to statistical analysis. Reporting from local laboratories was originally on a voluntary basis but became

⁹ Croatian Academy of Medical Sciences - Antibiotic resistance in Croatia (2022).

obligatory with accession to the EU. The network started collecting data on paper from local laboratories. The data manager at the reference centre would digitise the data. In 2020, it was agreed to officially transition to electronic data submission⁹.

For the purpose of reporting to TESSy, AMR data is collected on the WHONET software (a free desktop Windows application for the management and analysis of microbiology laboratory data)¹⁰, which is then used as a link for the EARS-Net TESSy system (The European Surveillance System - ECDC, integrated now in EpiPulse). This procedure allows data to be used and analysed at a national level, independently of the European dataset, which is not possible when data is entered directly into the TESSy system. The data on invasive isolates is also included as a chapter in national analyses, before the data become publicly available as part of European data. The benefits of this pathway that allows data analysis at country level were highlighted in the interviews.

In 2008, the Dutch Fund for Regional Partnerships (NFRP) / Matra financed the hiring of IT personnel to connect each local LIS to WHONET, successfully achieving electronic data transfer in several laboratories. However, a lack of resources for IT personnel meant that the laboratories had to move back to paper reporting. As of now, data transfer is again occurring electronically. The reference centre receives a WHONET file from each local laboratory, which is combined into a national file after scrutiny of the data. The WHONET system also allows for exporting data in .csv format.

Croatia also collects data on antimicrobial consumption, as part of the European Surveillance of Antimicrobial Consumption Network (ESAC-Net). Outpatient and hospital antibiotic consumption have been tracked separately. Data on the use of antibiotics is collected from HZZO. Outpatient antibiotic consumption data is collected from two sources: pharmaceutical wholesalers and Croatian Health Insurance Fund (CHIF) reimbursement data. The use of antibiotics in hospitals is comprised from two sources: wholesalers and hospital pharmacies¹¹.

AI solutions are not currently used in AMR surveillance in Croatia.

Point of entry testing is not conducted on a systematic basis in Croatia but can be performed if indicated. Point of entry testing is not integrated into the national surveillance system.

ii. Data linkage and sharing

Each laboratory has a LIS, which generates ID numbers that can be connected locally in the hospital with the OIB personal identifier used in Croatia.

Laboratories generally have to input data twice: once to their own system and once to WHONET. Given the relatively low number of cases of invasive isolates per laboratory, this double reporting is tolerated for EARS-Net. However, it would be less feasible to include all isolates, extracted to a universal platform, as not all laboratories have automatic extraction to WHONET. It was reported that there are plans to further digitalise the process and move towards automatic extraction to WHONET. The question remains whether all local laboratories would be willing to automatically extract their data to WHONET, as it raises questions of access to data and the responsibility for analysing the data. The CIPH is expected to take the lead for

¹⁰ [WHONET - Microbiology laboratory database software](#)

¹¹ [Croatian Academy of Medical Sciences - Antibiotic resistance in Croatia \(2022\)](#).

the legal aspects and dividing responsibilities for data analysis, providing a legal framework. Some laboratories use WHONET and send data directly, while others send data to the reference centre in other formats and the medical staff in the reference centre transform it locally. Croatia is striving to have all national data extracted to WHONET.

On antibiotic consumption in hospital, hospitals submit their data electronically to ISKRA. The preferred method of data delivery is to directly export data from hospital pharmacy programmes, however only a small proportion of hospitals do so. Once received, data is processed and sent back to each hospital for verification.

Data on AMR is shared internationally to the ECDC (TESSy) and WHO Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (GLASS). Croatia takes part in EARS-Net and the ESAC-Net of ECDC since joining the EU in 2013¹².

Nationally, AMR in animals is generally reported separately, but it is planned to have joint reporting from 2024.

iii. Data storage

There is currently no national IT infrastructure in place for storage and processing of all AMR data in Croatia. Data on AMR is stored locally at the *UHID Dr.Fran Mihaljević*, and the other mentioned sources.

iv. Standards and data quality

One of the objectives of the network of microbiological laboratories is to standardise the AMR surveillance system. Data on AMR is shared via standardised electronic reports.

Standardisation of the AMR surveillance has been a main objective since the creation of the laboratory network. Since 2011, the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) standards have been made a requirement for all laboratories in the surveillance network¹².

Specific codes are used for local sites, and the EARS-Net coding system is used.

For antibiotic consumption, data is collected in accordance with the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification of drugs. The use of antibiotics is expressed in defined daily doses per 1000 inhabitants per day (DDD/TID). Each antibiotic has a prescribed defined daily dose according to the Collaborating Centre for Drug Statistics Methodology (Oslo, Norway)¹².

There is no metadata catalogue available for AMR data.

Data is reported on a yearly basis in the annual "*Report on sensitivity and resistance of bacteria to antibiotics in the Republic of Croatia*", which is published by the Croatian Academy of Medical Sciences¹³. The report includes a chapter on invasive isolates, based on the data collected as part of EARS-Net surveillance, which is published before reporting to EARS-Net.

¹² [Croatian Academy of Medical Sciences - Antibiotic resistance in Croatia \(2022\).](#)

¹³ [Resistance of bacteria to antibiotics in Croatia - ISKRA](#)

v. Threat indicators

Threat detection for AMR is event-based. Threat detection and validation is not automated, it involves manual analysis by experts. If there is any deviation, this is discussed in the network.

Validated threats are reported internationally to EARS-Net.

In terms of management of an unknown threat, the reference centre would discuss directly with the local lab where the threat was detected and initiate early detection and tracing to contain the spread of the pathogen. The threat would also be notified to infection control within the Ministry of Health.

c. Legislation and strategy

There is agreement among all hospitals to send samples or results of AMR testing to the National Reference Laboratory at the UHID *Dr. Fran Mihaljević*. There are also agreements with ECDC/EARS-Net to send data internationally.

The Croatian AMR action plan, “*National Control Program for Antimicrobial Resistance 2017-2021*” is interdisciplinary, including human health, animal health, education and research¹⁴. It covers the surveillance of AMR in humans and animals, education on prudent use of antibiotics, and research in the area of antimicrobial resistance. The legislation providing the legal framework for antimicrobial resistance is not currently up to date.

¹⁴ [Croatian National control program for antimicrobial resistance 2017 - 2021. WHO](#)

III. Chemical threats

a. Key actors and stakeholder networks

Since 2019, the **Division for Toxicology** has been part of **CIPH**. Within the institute, all the heads of divisions have meetings twice a week to promote collaboration between the teams.

The Division of Toxicology holds the responsibility for receiving and checking correctness of safety data sheets of all chemicals entering and being produced in the country. Additionally, it conducts two courses on the safe handling of chemicals. The first course is designed for workers in the chemical industry, while the second targets managers and supervisors and it delves into detailed information on chemical legislation at both European and national level. Both trainings are conducted every so often, but persons working with chemicals attend one of courses every five years to ensure comprehensive knowledge updates.

The Division of Toxicology of CIPH actively participates in the Joint Action (JA) TERROR¹⁵. The main objectives of the JA are to address gaps in health preparedness and to strengthen cross-sectoral work with security, civil protection and health sectors response to biological and chemical terror attacks.

If Croatian firms have questions related to the Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) regulation¹⁶, they can communicate them to the Public Health Institute. If the institute is unable to provide an answer, they can bring the national question to Help Net¹⁷, a network made up of the European Chemical Agency (ECHA) and the national BPR (Biocidal Products Regulation¹⁸), CLP and REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals¹⁹) helpdesks.

The **Ministry of Interior** has a specialised service focused on CBRN. Formerly managed by the state directorate, this responsibility has now been absorbed by the MoI.

Inspection activities in the field of work and safety at work regarding chemicals, are performed by the sanitary inspection of the State Inspectorate²⁰.

Universities play a limited role in the formulation of new plans, procedures, or legislation, as their primary function in the country is limited to educational purposes. Their involvement is typically restricted to contributions through scientific papers, without direct engagement with the ministry or other stakeholders. In certain cases, professors may be invited to participate as experts. Medical students are provided with diverse specialization options, including crisis management and epidemiology. As part of the ongoing efforts to enhance medical education, courses addressing emergency, crisis, disaster, and incident management in public health are being integrated into the Medical University programme. These courses focus on equipping students with practical knowledge to effectively manage and respond to diverse health-related challenges. Emphasizing the importance of the One Health approach, the medical training curriculum is being further developed to include classes on the topic.

¹⁵ [Strengthened preparedness and response to biological and chemical terror attacks - Joint Action TERROR](#)

¹⁶ [CLP – Regulation \(EC\) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures](#)

¹⁷ [HelpNet - European Chemical Agency](#)

¹⁸ [BPR – Regulation \(EU\) No 528/2012 concerning the making available on the market and use of biocidal products](#)

¹⁹ [REACH - Regulation \(EC\) No 1907/2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals \(REACH\)](#)

²⁰ [Reporting to the Labour Department of the State Inspectorate - State Inspectorate Act, Official Gazette, No. 115/18, 117/21](#)

b. Digital infrastructures and systems

i. Data sources

The Toxicology division at CIPH oversees the publicly available database of safety data sheets of all chemicals being placed on Croatian market²¹. This is mandated via national law on chemicals. Also, all firms are mandated via a national ordinance to report information on all chemicals entering or produced within the country nationally, as there are no regional agencies. Currently, there is no automated system for the firms to submit data on incoming or produced chemicals, leading all stakeholders to share their reports via email or in a paper format. The responsible individual at the Public Health Institute manually inputs this data into their Register of import/production of Chemicals, with no current mechanism to detect underreporting from the industry. Despite plans to improve and centralize the system, insufficient funding remains a primary obstacle.

At the end of the year, the Public Health Institute manually compiles and share under request a comprehensive report to the Ministry of Health and/or Sanitary inspection. This report encompasses information on all firms involved in chemical production or importation in the country and the quantity of each chemical. The Ministry of Health/Sanitary inspection may subsequently request more detailed information, leading to the compilation of additional ad hoc reports.

When a new chemical is identified, it is added to the safety data sheet database. Information from the firm on the new chemical is emailed to the Public Health Institute, where it undergoes consistency checks according to Annex II of REACH regulation before being incorporated into their chemicals database. When safety data sheet is incorporated into safety data sheets database, chemical can be put on Croatian market. However, not all firms may be aware of this procedure, posing a risk of unregistered chemicals entering undetected. To mitigate this risk, the State Inspectorate conducts random sample checks on firms to ensure accurate chemical reporting.

The SCIP Database, Substances of Concern In articles as such or in complex objects (Products), was developed by the European Chemicals Agency and can be consulted by everyone since 24 September 2021. However, it is not highly used in Division for Toxicology.

ii. Data linkage and sharing

In regards of chemicals, no data is regularly shared at the European level. Punctual request by the Ministry can allow data to be shared with the European Commission.

iii. Standards and data quality

The country adheres to the standardised terminology from the ECHA, often referred to as the "*ECHA terminology*". ECHA develops and maintains standardized terminology to ensure consistency and clarity in communication related to chemicals and their regulatory processes within the European Union.

²¹ [Online Register of Chemicals - Division of Toxicology - CIPH](#)

iv. Threat indicators

The Toxicology division at CIPH manages the 24/7 emergency hotline for citizens and medical personnel encountering harmful or unknown chemicals. All calls are documented in an internal registry, but no annual report is currently produced nor required. Majority of calls are managed by telephone call, but sometimes, when a threat is identified and expert is requested at the site, the on-duty person visit the site, identifying the experts that should be involved. Firefighters, inspectorate, and other stakeholders may already be present, and decisions are made on task distribution. While there is no formalized procedure for chemical emergencies, there is a strong intention and ongoing discussions about the necessity to standardize the process.

Concerning MCM for chemical threats, the department consults its chemical database to determine the required equipment based on the threat. At the firm level, each company is responsible for providing PPE for their personnel. Every year, the institute purchase access to a medical database to verify symptoms and effects, the appropriate antidotes and treatment measures for various types of poisons.

Croatia also has a 24/7 National Poison Control Centre, obligated to compile an annual report on the calls received.

c. Legislation and strategy

Croatia has a national Chemicals Act which prescribes obligations for firms working with chemicals and four national ordinances concerning chemicals derive from the law.

The [National Ordinance and Chemical Reporting](#) mandates the reporting of all chemical production and imports, recognizing the potential variation in lists among European countries.

Firms working with ammonia and chlorine, or any other chemical which acts in gaseous form, reaching a predefined threshold, must contact the Public Health Institute for evaluation, as indicated in the [Ordinance on Chemicals in gas form](#). A representative from the institute conducts on-site assessments, evaluating the firm's operations, equipment safety and the efficacy of chemical anomaly detection systems. If necessary, recommendations for implementing changes to enhance establishment safety are provided. While no specific deadlines are initially stipulated, the Inspectorate can assign firms specific compliance deadlines after conducting inspections.

The [REACH Regulation](#) governs the safe use of chemicals within the European Union. It imposes obligations on companies to register and report information about the properties and uses of chemical substances.

The [Chemical Response Action](#) (determined by the nature of the incident) describes the roles of the different stakeholders. The Ministry handles intentional attacks, while the Public Health Institute takes responsibility for accidents, involving measurement, detection, and analysis.

Despite the existence of numerous protocols, a key challenge lies in ensuring their correct implementation and raising awareness among relevant stakeholders. Efforts are directed towards improving the effectiveness of protocol implementation mechanisms. Protocols are revised when needed, without strict revision cycles.

IV. Radiological and nuclear threats

The Republic of Croatia is a country without nuclear installations and without the intention to build such installations in the near future. In the early eighties of the last century state power utilities of Croatia and Slovenia constructed the Krsko Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) in Slovenian territory, some ten kilometres from the Croatian national border. Presently, two states share the nuclear liability and the ownership of the Krsko NPP. As the facility is located in Slovenia it is subject of Slovenian law, meaning that the Croatian regulatory body does not have any authorities regarding its operation²².

a. Key actors and stakeholder networks

The organization of an emergency management system for preparedness and response for nuclear or radiological emergencies is the responsibility of the **Ministry of the Interior (Mol)**. Implementation of protective actions is performed by the Civil Protection Commander who is supported by the **Civil Protection National Headquarters of the Republic of Croatia**. The Headquarters is staffed by representatives of all relevant ministries, governmental bodies and other organizations included in the response.

Radiological emergencies are not considered state-level emergencies and are handled by the licensee (facility that has been granted a license to use, handle, or work with radiological materials), Mol radiological emergency experts and local authorities.

The expert team of the Mol gives advice on protective actions to the Civil Protection Operational Headquarters (national and local) and licensee. In the event of a radiological emergency, the licensee is required to inform Mol immediately.

On the basis of the radiological and nuclear emergency response concept, a preparedness and response plan for the Republic of Croatia has been drawn up. This emergency plan includes a list of participants in the emergency preparedness and response (EPR) system:

- Holders of the approval for activities involving ionising radiation sources, including holders of the approval for transport of ionising radiation sources,
- Holders of the approval for performing a nuclear activity,
- Holders of the approval for performing operations involving radioactive waste and disused sources
- Scrap metal operators,
- Food and/or water business operators and - feed business operators,
- State administration bodies,
- Executive and representative bodies of local and regional self-government units,
- Civil protection system operational forces,
- Authorised technical services,
- Ionising radiation protection experts,
- Authorised experts for nuclear safety and
- Others that can contribute to the implementation of protection measures.

²² Croatian report on nuclear safety - 9th Croatian national report on the implementation of the Obligations under the Convention on Nuclear Safety - Republic of Croatia (2022)

The state administration bodies referred to are:

- Ministry Competent for Internal Affairs,
- Ministry Competent for Health,
- Ministry Competent for Agriculture,
- Ministry Competent for Defence,
- Ministry Competent for Finance,
- Ministry Competent for Economy,
- Ministry Competent for Social Policy,
- Ministry Competent for European and Foreign Affairs And
- National Meteorological and Hydrological Service.

The licensee is also required to make an initial provisional assessment of the emergency and its possible consequences and for carrying out urgent protective measures within the facility. It is not expected that urgent protective actions would need to be taken outside of the facility for operators in Croatia.

Engagement with international organizations plays a key role in management and preparedness for health emergencies related to nuclear and radiological threats and it includes collaboration with entities such as the European Commission (EC), the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), national public health agencies, the United Nations conventions, facilitating early notifications and information exchange mechanisms. Bilateral agreements with neighbouring countries, specifically Slovenia and Hungary, are essential due to the shared responsibility for a nuclear plant, fostering efficient communication and resource sharing in emergency scenarios.

b. Digital infrastructures and systems

i. Data sources

Data is systematically gathered at the national, regional and local levels however, the country lacks a centralized platform at the national level. The existing system for communication and exchange relies on national warning points that operate 24/7. When a warning signal is identified the information is manually shared with other centres across the national territory via fax, emails or phone calls. While there is a desire to transition to a more digitalised and automated system, no specific plans for its implementation are currently in place.

The early warning system in Croatia is comprised of thirty-three stations positioned along the borders of the country. This system is designed to automatically detect anomalies or instances where values surpass predefined thresholds. Once triggered, inspectors within the MoI are promptly informed and activated. In cases requiring an intervention, a response team is mobilized, the composition of which is defined depending on the nature of the threat. Within the national emergency plan, the outlining of specific responsibilities and actions of the stakeholders involved is described.

The systems in place do not offer functionalities to present or export data, such as dashboards, reports, APIs (Application Programming Interface), and business intelligence tools. AI solutions are not currently implemented nor considered a priority for the development within the nuclear and radiological information systems.

The country collects data at designated PoE (i.e. specific border crossings) however, this data is not integrated into the national surveillance system.

ii. Data linkage and sharing

Croatia and Slovenia jointly operate a nuclear plant and extensively share related data with international stakeholders. This collaborative approach is vital in addressing potential challenges beyond national borders.

Croatia actively shares data with pertinent EU and international organizations via EWRS. This collaborative effort extends to the dissemination of measurement results obtained from monitoring stations, encompassing dose rates and other relevant metrics.

For exchanging information internationally, the country uses the Information Exchange in Incidents and Emergencies (USIE), a secure website maintained by the IAEA to enable countries to exchange urgent notifications and follow-up information during an emergency²³. This system is designed for international information exchange, enabling the finding and dissemination of information.

iii. Data storage

The country has a national/regional IT infrastructure dedicated to the storage and processing of nuclear and radiological data. Within the framework of the EWRS, there is a regular input of data and standardized forms and templates to ensure uniformity in data capture and reporting procedures are used.

iv. Standards and data quality

At the national level, reports do not have specific templates and the information reported varies depending on the needs of the request or threat. However, standardized templates are employed at the international level, both within the European context and for countries affiliated with the United Nations.

v. Threat indicators

Nuclear or radiological health threats are identified through an event-based approach. The automated primary inspection at the border handles threat detection, assessment, and initial evaluation. Subsequently, a secondary inspection is initiated, featuring the active participation of experts.

²³ [Emergency notification and reporting - International Atomic Energy Agency](#)

c. Legislation and strategy

Key legislatures that define emergency preparedness and response system for radiological and nuclear threats are:

- [Act on Radiological and Nuclear Safety](#) (OG 141/13, 39/15, 130/17, 118/18, 21/22, 114/22) focusing on emergency response at the national level;
- [Regulation on Measures for Protection Against Ionising Radiation and Activities in Case of Emergency](#) (OG 24/18, 70/20, 114/21);
- Preparedness and Response Plan of the Republic of Croatia to a Radiological or Nuclear Emergency.

The Mol is tasked with the preparation of a national emergency response plan, with the most recent iteration adopted in February 2022. According to the Plan, all stakeholders bear the responsibility of formulating their individual emergency response plans and procedures. Recognizing the collaborative nature of this effort, various stakeholders have the option to seek support from the Mol in the development of their respective plans.

Regarding MCM, the Ministry of Health bears the responsibility for formulating plans concerning the procurement and storage of essential equipment required for diverse emergency scenarios. Collaborative agreements have been established to facilitate the sharing of equipment with other countries during emergencies, exemplified by the understanding with iodine thyroid blocking (ITB) tablets. 100,000 ITB tablets are stored in two locations in Croatia, ready for distribution in case of emergencies. In the event of an emergency, a swift and coordinated response is paramount. Within one hour, Croatia, Slovenia, and Hungary should be ready to share ITB resources, ensuring efficient distribution where needed in the field.

In the country, there are comprehensive agreements among stakeholders and regions to facilitate data sharing, both nationally and internationally. The legal framework supporting these agreements is up to date and the nation has proactive pandemic preparedness plans in place. However, in the context of implementing response and protective measures, there is a lack of harmonization across neighbouring countries. This disparity is exemplified by the divergence in protective measures adopted during a general emergency – Croatia adopts a twenty kilometres protective radius, while Slovenia adheres to a 10 kilometres radius, creating significant gaps along the border. This highlights the pressing need for increased harmonization, particularly within Europe.

Croatia adheres to international guidelines and frameworks for preparedness and response to nuclear or radiological emergencies. One of the key international instruments in this regard is the "*Convention on Early Notification of a Nuclear Accident*²⁴" and the "*Convention on Assistance in the Case of a Nuclear Accident or Radiological Emergency*²⁵", both developed by IAEA.

²⁴ [Information circular 335 - Convention On Early Notification Of A Nuclear Accident - IAEA](#)

²⁵ [Information circular 336 - Convention On Assistance In The Case Of A Nuclear Accident Or Radiological Emergency - IAEA](#)

Agreements with the neighbouring countries to receive and send information and MCM (via the AIE system) in case of need, as well as via internal channel USIE, are in place.

To be better prepared, simulation exercises are organised regularly. Following each exercise, stakeholders are mandated to identify gaps in their response plans and assess the need for improvements in the procedures followed. Presently, every stakeholder engaged in nuclear or radiological activities within the country is actively undertaking the development or update of their response plans. However, there is a lack of training on emergency protocols and simulation exercises specific for doctors to enhance preparedness at all levels. Furthermore, there is a notable absence of clear information about the designated hospital in the event of a nuclear or radiological emergency.

A significant gap resides in stakeholders' incomplete awareness of their respective obligations, including training, procedure development, and plan updates. The MoI assumes responsibility for ensuring compliance with these obligations. Subsequently, the MoI reviews the plans and issues either approval or recommendations for improvements. The overarching objective is to foster harmonization in response efforts among the stakeholders.

V. Medical countermeasures

a. Key actors and stakeholder networks

As defined in the Croatian Law on Strategic Stocks, the procurement of commodity stocks, the storage of commodity stocks, the leasing of unused warehouse space and the renewal of commodity stocks are performed by the **Directorate for Commodity Inventories** as an administrative organization within the **Ministry for the Economy**.

The **Croatian Parliament** establishes the **Council for Commodity Stocks** to supervise the management of commodity stocks, upon the proposal of the competent committee of the Croatian Parliament. The Council for Commodity Stocks consists of three representatives of the Croatian Parliament and two experts in the field of economy. The Council for Commodity Stocks considers the proposal for the Balance Sheet and the Annual Program of Strategic Commodity Stocks (Article 9), and quarterly reports on the state and management of commodity stocks and the annual report on the state and management of commodity stock.

In the management of commodity stocks, the **Government of the Republic of Croatia** adopts the Annual Program and determines the annual Report on the state and management of commodity stocks, which it submits to the Croatian Parliament; makes decisions on the sale of real estate that is no longer needed for the storage of goods, and that is owned by the Republic of Croatia; makes decisions on the sale of goods from stock; makes decisions on the transfer of individual goods stocks with or without compensation to organizations, associations and units of local and regional self-government; decides on replenishment of goods stocks.

As per updates in the Healthcare Act in 2023, **CIPH** is responsible for designing and maintaining a National Register of Equipment in the healthcare system (see below). The manner of maintaining the register and the data it contains are decided through an ordinance by the **Minister for Health**.

b. Legislation and strategy

The [Croatian Law on Strategic Stocks](#) “*regulates the conditions for the creation, financing, use and renewal of commodity stocks*”, including the provision of space for storage of stocks and renewal of stock inventory.

As of December 2022, the law was updated to include medicines and medical products in the stockpiling strategy. As such, the law states that stocks consist of “*agricultural, food and non-food products, as well as medicines, vaccines, antidotes, medical products, medical materials and protective equipment that are absolutely necessary for human life*”. The law includes a list of the specific medicines and medical products included in stockpiling. However, stockpiling of medicines is not yet implemented since the update of the law. The process will be coordinated by the Ministry of Health, including creating a register for monitoring stocks. In this way, Croatia does not currently have stockpiles of medical countermeasures for national use during a public health emergency. The only existing stockpiles are of protective equipment, which was brought in during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Under the Law on Strategic Stocks, every year a Balance Sheet is revised, which specifies the type, name and quantity of goods in the inventory, as well as their geographical distribution.

The geographical distribution of the stocks is classified if sharing their location could harm national security or the execution of tasks by state bodies.

Based on the Balance Sheet, the Government of Croatia adopts an annual programme, including financial plans to procure or renew stocks.

Civil protection monitors food and blankets, but there is no specific system for monitoring the quantity of medicines and PPE. Certain details, such as stockpile locations, are considered confidential information.

Amendments to the [Healthcare Act](#) introduced in March 2023 specify that a National Register of Equipment should be created. The process of designing and maintaining the register is under the responsibility of CIPH with the Ministry of Health.

c. Data collection on MCM

Currently, data is not systematically collected on medical countermeasures.

Croatia has a national stockpiling system with a central management system, which covers different products, not specific to medical countermeasures. When an alert is activated, the Ministry of Economy puts in place a procedure to order the missing products. CIPH is responsible for medical devices, and has been involved in collecting data from hospitals, mainly on respirators and PPE. CIPH is developing a register of all medical equipment in the Croatian healthcare system. The Ministry of Health will be able to derive data from this system.

Procedures differ depending on the context. Under normal times, the Ministry of the Interior is responsible for the stockpiling of all medical equipment. During crisis management, such as during the COVID-19 pandemic, data relating to medical equipment could have been collected using alternative methods (e.g. informal contacts between responsible persons).

d. IT system for stockpile monitoring

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the Ministry of Health built two information systems for immunisation purposes: one for stockpiles and management of vaccines, and the other for immunisation registration. Both are logical parts of CEZIH infrastructure and processes. These systems were built to support and monitor vaccines distribution and immunisation coverage.

i. Vaccine stockpile monitoring

The system to stockpile, monitor and distribute vaccines is called the Central place for Receiving, Distributing and Monitoring the Vaccine inventory of the Republic of Croatia (Croatian acronym: eCEZDLIH). It is part of CEZIH, and uses its credentials in order to enable all the players of the distribution chain, healthcare providers and contracted distributors to stockpile, order, distribute, depose and use available vaccines.

There is two ways for healthcare providers to enter data in eCEZDLIH: if the IT system used by the health institution is connected to eCEZDLIH, it is entered in the institution's IT system

which then automatically sends data to eCEZDLIH; if the IT system of the health institution is not connected to eCEZDLIH, the institution must enter it directly into eCEZDLIH²⁶.

There is no specific process implemented yet to identify potential issues, risks, stockpiling bottlenecks, disruption, vulnerabilities for the supply chain of medical countermeasures in Croatia. A Health System Performance Assessment (HSPA) was performed in 2023, the information from which is used to evaluate bottlenecks and shortages. The Agency for Medicinal Products and Medical Devices of Croatia (Agencija za lijekove i medicinske proizvode – English acronym: HALMED) reports on shortages of medicines.

There is no automated system or threshold set to activate deployment of stockpiles, and no IT system in place (e.g. AI driven, business intelligence) for managing stockpile quantities.

ii. Immunisation registry

The immunisation registry (e-Vaccination, e-Vac database) serves as a central database of all registered vaccinations. It is also a part of CEZIH, uses its credentials in order to enable all health care providers who are conducting immunisations to register each individual procedure (ATC code of the vaccine, vaccine name, manufacturer, number of dose received – 1st, 2nd, 3rd, booster etc.- serial number of the vaccine administered, date and place of vaccination, etc.). Resulting, it became a source for Central e-Vaccination card of the Republic of Croatia as well as European digital COVID certificate.

e. Reporting (internationally and nationally)

The Directorate for Commodity Inventories submits quarterly reports on the commodity stocks to the Minister for Economy. Once a year, the Government submits a report to the Croatian Parliament on the state and management of commodity stocks for the previous year²⁷. Croatia does not report internationally on orders, stocks and availability of MCM.

f. Monitoring of effectiveness

There is no IT system to monitor the effectiveness and impact of deployed medical countermeasures.

²⁶ [Vaccination plan against COVID-19. Data entry IT system eCEZDLIH eCIJEPIH instructions - Croatian Ministry of Health](#)

²⁷ [Law on Strategic Commodity Stocks - Government of the Republic of Croatia \(last updated 14 December 2022\)](#)

CONCLUSION

This report presents the findings of the country visit in Croatia as part of the EU-HIP project, which aimed to collect additional information on digital systems for surveillance and monitoring of PHPP, AMR, CBRN threats and MCM. The content of the report reflects the information collected via the initial landscape analysis, as well as the interviews carried out in November 2023.

The purpose of collecting and compiling this country-specific material was to make available, to the country and the experts working on building the ATHINA platform, an initial state-of-play of the national IT systems in place for health threats surveillance and to support further work within the EU-HIP project.

For this upcoming work, the identification of key areas of improvement and actions to strive towards interoperability with the ATHINA platform are needed. In this regard, the next phase of the EU-HIP project involves evaluating the specific technical needs to strengthen health information systems at the country level. The objective of this stage is to examine the technical necessities and work on improving the digital epidemiological surveillance infrastructure for early detection and assessment of health threat and events on a national level. Countries that participate in a country visit will be able to benefit from the findings in the country report to identify their technical needs. These enhancements include developing new systems and processes, building upon, complementing, or expanding existing IT frameworks, as well as further digitising workflows.

A second objective of the EU-HIP project is to work in parallel with the improvement of digital surveillance, towards harmonisation of IT systems and infrastructures at the level of EU Member States with a view to secure and semi-automated data transfer to ATHINA. Therefore, recommendations regarding country specific needs to be considered during the development of the ATHINA platform, and in a broader context for enhancing collaboration across Europe, were collected during the interviews. Those insights will guide upcoming discussions with HERA regarding the development of ATHINA and the EU-HIP future work.

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Appendix 1. Information collected through a mandatory infectious disease notification' case.

N°	DATA	DESCRIPTION
1	Serial number of the application for mandatory notification of infectious diseases	Code of the doctor who sends the application + date and time of sending the application + serial number of the application (in year)
2	Ordination number	Taken from the Registry of health institutions and ambulances (at CIPH)
3	Doctor number	Taken from the Registry of healthcare workers (at CIPH)
4	Surname	
5	Name	
6	Name of Father	
7	Date of birth	ISO 8601 and HL7 adapted ISO 8601 format
8	Gender/Sex	Code from the Gender code list
9	Country	Only for non-Croatian citizens
10	Place of work/school	Name of the organization where the patient is employed or studies
11	Occupation/work performed	Code from the codebook of occupations
12	City/municipality of the disease	City or municipality where the patient is currently located. This does not have to be the place where the patient is permanently registered
13	County of the disease	The county where the patient is currently located. This does not have to be the place where the patient is permanently registered
14	Address	Street and house number where the patient is currently located. This does not have to be the place where the patient is permanently registered
15	Diagnosis	ICD-10 Code
16	The causative agent	
17	Method of determining the disease	Code from the codebook of Diagnostics: clinical, laboratory, clinical + laboratory
18	Has the patient been vaccinated against this disease?	YES/NO/UNKNOWN/NOT FULLY
19	Date of last vaccination	It is entered if the patient was vaccinated against the diagnosed disease
20	Date of illness	ISO 8601 and HL7 adapted ISO 8601 format
21	Date of death	ISO 8601 and HL7 adapted ISO 8601 format

Appendix 2. List of infectious diseases under the Law of Population Protection from Infectious diseases (Croatian - English)

Are highlighted those part of the pathogens with high pandemic potential's list of the EU-HIP project.

1. *Aktivna tuberkuloza (Active tuberculosis)*
2. *Akutna mlohava paraliza (Acute flaccid paralysis)*
3. *Amebijaza (Amebiasis)*
4. *Bakterijska sepsa (Bacterial sepsis)*
5. *Bakterijski meningitis (Bacterial meningitis)*
6. *Bjesnoća (Rabies)*
7. *Botulizam (Botulism)*
8. *Brill-Zinsserova bolest (Brill-Zinsser disease)*
9. *Bruceloza (Brucellosis)*
10. *Creutzfeldt-Jakobova bolest (Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease)*
11. *Crni prišt (Anthrax)*
12. *Crvenka / Kongenitalna rubeolarna embriopatija (Rubeola / Congenital rubeolar embryopathy)*
13. *Denga groznica (Dengue fever)*
14. *Difterija (Diphtheria)*
15. *Dizenterija (Dysentery)*
16. *Dječja paraliza (Poliomyelitis)*
17. *EHEC-bolest uzrokovana enterohemoragičnom Esherichia coli / infekcija s E.coli koja producira shiga / vero toksin (EHEC-disease caused by enterohemorrhagic Esherichia coli / infection with Shiga-producing E.coli / Vero toxin)*
18. *Ehinokokoza (Echinococcosis)*
19. *Enterokolitis (Enterocolitis)*
20. *Enteroviroze (Enterovirosis)*
21. *Erizipel (Erysipelas)*
22. *Erlihioza (Erlchyosis)*
23. *Fasciolijaza (Fascioliasis)*
24. *Gripa (Influenza)*
25. *Gripa Ptičja (Avian influenza (A/H5 - A/H5N1))*
26. *Gripa uzrokovana novim influenza virusom (Flu caused by novel influenza viruses)*
27. *Guba (Leprosy)*
28. *Helmintoze (Helminth infections)*
29. *Hemoragijska groznica s bubrežnim sindromom / Hemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome (HFRS caused by hantaviruses)*
30. *Herpes zoster (Shingles)*
31. *Hripavac (Whooping cough)*
32. *Infekcijska mononukleoza (Infectious mononucleosis)*
33. *Invazivna bolest uzrokovana Hamophilusom influenzae tipa B (Invasive disease caused by Heamophilus influenzae type B)*
34. *Invazivna bolest uzrokovana Streptokokom pneumoniae (Invasive disease caused by Streptococcus pneumoniae)*
35. *Jersinioza (Yersiniosis)*
36. *Kala-Azar, visceralna lišmanijaza (Visceral leishmaniasis)*
37. *Kampilobakterioza (Campylobacteriosis)*
38. *Kapavac (Gonorrhoea)*
39. *Klamidijaza (Chlamydia)*

40. *Kliconoštvo salmonellae (Germination of Salmonellae)*
41. *Kliconoštvo salmonellae typhi (Germination of Salmonella typhi)*
42. *Kolera (Cholera)*
43. *Kongenitalna toksoplazmoza (Congenital toxoplasmosis)*
44. *Kongenitalni i neonatalni sifilis (Congenital and neonatal syphilis)*
45. *Kriptosporidioza (Cryptosporidiosis)*
46. *Krpeljni meningoencefalitis (Tick-borne meningoencephalitis)*
47. *Kuga (Plague)*
48. *Lambliasis (Giardiasis)*
49. *Legionarska bolest i legioneloze (Legionnaires' disease and legionellosis)*
50. *Leptospiroze (Leptospirosis)*
51. *Listerioza (Listeriosis)*
52. *Lišmanijaza kožna (Cutaneous Leishmaniasis)*
53. *Lyme borelijoza (Lyme borreliosis)*
54. *Lymphogranuloma venerum (Venereal lymphogranuloma)*
55. *Malaria (Malaria)*
56. *Mediteranska pjegava groznica (Mediterranean spotted fever)*
57. *Meningokokni meningitis / sepsa (Meningococcal meningitis / sepsis)*
58. *Murini tifus (Murini typhus)*
59. *Nosilac HBs Ag (Carrier of Hepatitis B surface antigen)*
60. *Nosilac HCV protutijela (Carrier of Hepatitis C virus antibodies)*
61. *Nosilac HIV protutijela (HIV infekcija) (Carrier of HIV antibodies (HIV infection))*
62. *Ornitoza-psitakoza (Ornithosis-Psittacosis)*
63. *Ospice (Measles)*
64. *Papatači groznica (Fever sufferer)*
65. *Pjegavac (Typhus)*
66. *Povratna groznica (Relapsing fever, Malaria-like illnesses)*
67. *Q groznica (Q fever)*
68. *Rickettsiosis (Rickettsiosis)*
69. *Salmoneloza (Salmonellosis)*
70. **SARS (Severe Acute Respiratory Syndromes)**
71. *Sifilis (Syphilis)*
72. *Sindrom stečenog nedostatka imuniteta (Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome)*
73. *Streptokokna upala grla (Streptococcal sore throat / angina)*
74. *Svrab (Scabies)*
75. *Šarlah (Scarlet fever)*
76. *Tetanus (Tetanos)*
77. *Toksoplazmoza (Toxoplasmosis)*
78. *Trbušni tifus (Typhoid fever)*
79. *Trihinelozna (Trichinosis)*
80. *Trovanje hranom (osim salmonela) (Food poisoning except Salmonella)*
81. *Tularemija (Tularemia)*
82. *Upala pluća (Pneumonia, bronchopneumonia)*
83. *Ušljivost glave/tijela (Head / Body infection by louse)*
84. *Velike boginje (Smallpox)*
85. **Virusna hemoragijska groznica (Viral haemorrhagic fever)**
86. *Virusni gastroenterokolitis (Viral gastroenterocolitis)*
87. *Virusni hepatitis A (Viral Hepatitis A)*
88. *Virusni hepatitis B (Viral Hepatitis B)*
89. *Virusni hepatitis C (Viral Hepatitis C)*

90. *Virusni hepatitis D (Viral Hepatitis D)*
91. *Virusni hepatitis E (Viral Hepatitis E)*
92. *Virusni hepatitis G (Viral Hepatitis G)*
93. *Virusni hepatitis neoznačeni (Viral hepatitis unlabeled)*
94. *Virusni meningitis (Viral meningitis)*
95. *Vodene kozice (Varicella)*
96. *West Nile groznica (West Nile fever)*
97. *Zarazna upala mozga (Encephalitis)*
98. *Zaušnjaci (Mumps)*
99. *Žuta groznica (Yellow fever)*

Appendix 3. List of goods that may constitute strategic commodity stocks from the Law on Strategic Commodity Stocks Act 2002 – 2022 NN 141/22 by the Directorate for Commodity Stocks, Ministry of Economy (Croatian - English)

POLJOPRIVREDNI I PREHRAMBENI PROIZVODI (AGRICULTURAL AND FOOD PRODUCTS)

1. *Žitarice i prerađevine od žitarica (Cereals and cereal products)*
2. *Meso i mesne prerađevine (Meat and meat products)*
3. *Mlijeko i mliječne prerađevine (Milk and dairy products)*
4. *Jaja (Eggs)*
5. *Voda (Water)*
6. *Ostali poljoprivredni i prehrambeni proizvodi koje odredi Vlada Bilancom (Other agricultural and food products determined by the Government Balance Sheet)*

NEPREHRAMBENI PROIZVODI (NON-FOOD PRODUCTS)

1. *Naftni derivati (Petroleum products)*
2. *Građevinski materijali (Building materials)*
3. *Proizvodi od plastičnih masa (Plastics products)*
4. *Vozila, agregati, pumpe i plovila (Véhicules, aggregates, pumps and vessels)*
5. *Oprema i roba za opskrbu, smještaj i zdravstveno zbrinjavanje stanovništva (Equipment and goods for supply, accommodation and health care of the population)*
6. *Oprema za zaštitu od poplava (Flood protection equipment)*
7. *Sredstva za asanaciju, dezinfekciju, dezinfekciju i deratizaciju (Means for assanation, disinfection, disinsection and pest control)*
8. *Ostali neprehrambeni proizvodi koje odredi Vlada Bilancom (Other non-food products determined by the Government Balance Sheet)*

LIJEKOVI, CJEPIVA, PROTUOTROVI, MEDICINSKI PROIZVODI, MEDICINSKI MATERIJAL I ZAŠTITNA OPREMA (MEDICINAL PRODUCTS, VACCINES, ANTIDOTES, MEDICAL DEVICES, MEDICAL SUPPLIES AND PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT)

1. *Antibiotici (Antibiotics)*
2. *Lijekovi za liječenje virusnih infekcija (Medicines for the treatment of viral infections)*
3. *Antimikotici, antibiotici, kemoterapeutici i kortikosteroidi za lokalnu primjenu (Antimycotics, antibiotics, chemotherapeutics and corticosteroids for topical use)*
4. *Oftalmici (Opthalmics)*
5. *Analgetici i lijekovi za palijativnu njegu (Analgesics and drugs for palliative care)*
6. *Antialergici i lijekovi za anafilaksiju (Antiallergics and drugs for anaphylaxis)*
7. *Anestetici (Anesthetics)*
8. *Antikonvulzivni lijekovi i anksiolitici (Anticonvulsant drugs and anxiolytics)*
9. *Antipsihotici (Antipsychotics)*
10. *Kardiovaskularni lijekovi (Cardiovascular drugs)*
11. *Gastrointestinalni lijekovi (Gastrointestinal drugs)*
12. *Inzulini i ostali lijekovi za dijabetes (Insulins and other drugs for diabetes)*
13. *Lijekovi koji djeluju na respiratorni sustav (Drugs that act on the respiratory system)*
14. *Otopine za rehidraciju i acidobazne poremećaje (Solutions for rehydration and acid-base disorders)*
15. *Cjepiva (Vaccines)*
16. *Imunoglobulini (Immunoglobulins)*
17. *Protuotrovi (antidoti)(Antidotes)*

18. *Medicinske otopine (Medical solutions)*
19. *Medicinski materijal i zaštitna oprema (Medical supplies and protective equipment)*
20. *Ostali medicinski proizvodi koje odredi Vlada Bilancom (Other medical devices designated by the Government of the Balance Sheet)*

